

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

This documentation provides a list and detailed description of supplementary output statistics that will be implemented in order to enable the science of WP9.

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WP8, Storms & Land

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1 Executive summary

This documentation provides a description of supplementary output diagnostics that were implemented, either online in the two NextGEMS models or offline as a postprocessing step, in order to enable the science of WP9 and the pilot project on solar power (task 8.4).

2 Conclusion & Results

The planned science of WP9 requires the computation of blocking indices, extreme indices as well as fire weather indices, whereas the pilot project on solar energy requires information on solar power. We ensured first that the necessary variables to compute these indices and to conduct the pilot project on solar energy are outputted in the two NextGEMS models at the requested temporal and spatial resolution. When not present, we added new variables in the output, such as potential vorticity or solar radiation in different wavelengths. Second, we prepared/collected postprocessing routines so that the indices can be computed in a postprocessing step using the outputted variables as input. Those postprocessing routines are either python-based routines, that can be freely downloaded from git repositories, or already existing functions from freely available software.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no
O3	
To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:	
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP8	Relevance in this deliverable?
Evaluate surface energy, water and momentum balance components as well as near-surface meteorology over land at storm-resolving resolution against observations and coarser resolution simulations (O1)	no
Represent land-surface heterogeneities at storm-resolving resolution by making use of the latest generation remote sensing products of land cover and vegetation (O1)	no
Prepare the NextGEMS models to best serve the science and applications, by implementing online output statistics co-developed with stakeholders, with a pilot project focusing on solar energy (O1 and O3)	yes
Expand scope of the SR-ESM by coupling it offline to a terrestrial biosphere model (O1)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

This deliverable is linked to task 8.4 of the NextGEMS project. As written in the proposal, in this task, online and offline output statistics needed for the science proposed in WP9 will be developed. The required statistics are blocking indices (for WP 9.1), extreme indices (for WP 9.2 and 9.5) as well as fire weather indicators (for WP 9.5). Moreover, statistics required for the proposed pilot project on solar energy will be developed with stakeholders and implemented.

In the following, we describe the supplementary output statistics needed for the science (section 4.1) and for the pilot project on solar energy (section 4.2) that were developed/implemented. To

be able to compute these statistics during the later analysis phase of the project, we especially ensure that the two NextGEMS models, ICON and IFS, provide the necessary input variables at the required temporal and spatial resolution.

4.1 Required indices for the science

Table 3 summarizes the implemented output statistics. More detail on their computation is given in the respective subsections below.

New diagnostics	Needed model output	Reference
AGP	ϕ_{500} , 6 hourly	Scherrer et al. (2006)
Absolute VAPV	PV, 3D, 6 hourly	Scherrer et al. (2006)
Anomaly VAPV	PV, 3D, 6 hourly	Scherrer et al. (2006)
Weather regimes	ϕ_{500} , 6 hourly	Grams et al. (2017)
EP-flux	u, v, ϕ, qv, T , 3D, 6 hourly	Edmon et al. (1980)
EGR	u, θ , 3D, 6 hourly	Simmonds and Lim (2009)
CDD	Precipitation, daily	Sandstad et al. (2022)
WSD	2-m T , daily maximum	Sandstad et al. (2022)
T_{wb}	2-m T, qv, p , hourly	Stipanuk (1973)
R99p	Precipitation, daily	Sandstad et al. (2022)
R20mm	Precipitation, daily	Sandstad et al. (2022)
FWIs	2-m T, qv , 10-m wind, 12 pm, precipitation (24 h)	Wagner and Pickette (1985)

Table 3: Diagnostics required for the science proposed in WP9 that were implemented. All indices are computed at a postprocessing step. The variables needed for their computation, which needs to be present in the NextGEMS output, are listed in the second column. Reference gives papers that have described the computation of the diagnostics, whose method we followed. Abbreviations are explained in the main text. The 3D variables are outputted at the following pressure levels in IFS and ICON: 1, 10, 30, 50, 70, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 400, 500, 600, 700, 750, 800, 850, 875, 900, 925, 950, 975, 1000 hPa.

Figure 1: Example of detected atmospheric blocks in ICON for a ten-day period. Shading for 500-hPa geopotential anomalies (blue negative, red positive), dots for detected blocks based on the AGP index.

4.1.1 Blocking/Circulation

Blocking indices are computed following Scherrer et al. (2006), who proposed three indicators to characterize atmospheric blocking. The first index is the absolute geopotential height (AGP) index. Its computation only requires geopotential height at 500 hPa, ϕ_{500} , a variable outputted per default in ICON and IFS. Based on ϕ_{500} , AGP is computed offline as a post-processing step. The routines needed to compute AGP can be found in this GIT repository: <https://github.com/lukasbrunner/blocking>. In our NextGEMS cycle 2 Hackathon, these routines have been applied to the output of the NextGEMS cycle 2 simulations to detect atmospheric blocks, see Fig. 1 as an example result.

The second and third blocking indices are dynamical indicators developed to capture the three-dimensional structure of the upper-tropospheric dynamical core of an atmospheric block. Their computation requires vertically averaged potential vorticity (VAPV), with the vertical average taken between 500 and 150 hPa. One index is based on closed contour of the absolute VAPV field, the other one on closed contour of the anomaly VAPV field. To that aim, we first implement potential vorticity (PV) as a new online output variable in ICON. In IFS, PV is already available as output. Second, both in ICON and IFS, PV is integrated as a postprocessing step and the obtained VAPV is used to detect and track atmospheric blocks. The corresponding postprocessing code can be found in this GIT repository: <https://github.com/steidani/ConTrack>

Besides atmospheric blocking, other weather regimes exist. Grams et al. (2017) proposed a classification of seven weather regimes designed to capture the year-round, large-scale flow variability in the Atlantic-European region. To distinguish these weather regimes, 500-hPa geopotential height is needed. As mentioned above, this variable is available as output from the ICON and IFS models. We then use the code provided by the Earth System Model eValuation tool, available here https://github.com/ESMValGroup/ESMValTool/blob/main/doc/sphinx/source/recipes/recipe_modes_of_variability.rst, to diagnose the corresponding weather regimes.

Finally, to further diagnose the atmospheric circulation and especially the underlying processes controlling its strength, we consider two further diagnostics. The first one is Eliassen-Palm flux (EP-flux). It allows to diagnose the forcing of the zonal-mean circulation state by eddies (see e.g. Edmon et al. 1980). Computation of EP-flux requires horizontal wind components (u and v), geopotential height ϕ , specific humidity qv and temperature T as a function of height (pressure) as input. Those variables are directly available from the output of ICON and IFS. We then compute the EP-flux offline as a postprocessing step, the postprocessing routine can be found

Figure 2: CDD computed for the ICON (left) and IFS (right) models.

here: <https://github.com/kuchaale/EPFD/>.

The second diagnostic of the atmospheric circulation is the eddy growth rate (EGR). Its computation requires potential temperature (θ) and zonal wind component (u), on pressure levels, that we correspondingly output in ICON and IFS. We then compute the eddy growth rate as a post-processing step using the function provided by the NCL software (https://www.ncl.ucar.edu/Document/Functions/Contributed/eady_growth_rate.shtml).

4.1.2 Extreme

For the science proposed in WP9.2 on dry and warm spells, we need to compute the following two extreme indices (see also summary in Tab. 3): consecutive dry days (CDD) and warm spell duration (WSD). CDD is defined as the annual maximum number of days in a row with precipitation below 1 mm (see Sandstad et al. 2022). It is a frequently used index to characterize the longest period in a year without rain, and hence the severity of dry spells. It will be used in WP9.2 (deliverable 9.2) to investigate the hypothesis that coarse-resolution models overestimate the length of dry spells due to the tendency of their convective parameterization to drizzle as compared to storm-resolving simulations.

To compute CDD, we need daily accumulated precipitation from IFS and ICON. With the update to the new hierarchical output, we now save precipitation as output frequencies of 30 minutes, 3 hourly and daily. We can thus directly access the daily output and then use the python function `xclim.indices.maximum_consecutive_dry_days` to compute CDD. The latter python function is part of the python package `xclim.indices`, see <https://xclim.readthedocs.io/en/stable/indices.html>, which provides function in python to compute climate indices, including CDD. As an example, Figure 2 shows the computed CDD for the ICON and IFS models, zooming over Europe.

WSD is defined as the annual count of days with at least 6 consecutive days when daily maximum temperature is above the calendar day 90th percentile of maximum temperature. It is the pendant to CDD, but characterizing a "dry and warm" spell not through its lack of precipitation but through its warm temperature. To compute it, we need the value of the daily maxi-

```
[63]: import intake
import xarray as xr

#Read data
cat = intake.open_catalog("https://data.nextgems-h2020.eu/catalog.yaml")
ds = cat.ICON.ngc3028(zoom=0, time="PT30M").to_dask()

[64]: # Compute maximum daily temperature
tdaily=ds.tas.resample(time='1D').max()

[65]: from xclim.core.calendar import percentile_doy
from xclim.indices import warm_spell_duration_index

#Compute WSD
tasmax_per = percentile_doy(tdaily, per=90).sel(percentiles=90)
wsd=warm_spell_duration_index(tdaily, tasmax_per)
```

Figure 3: Example Jupyter notebook to compute WSD. The length of the simulation (5 years) is too short to give at the moment meaningful results but this will be possible with the production runs.

imum temperature, which is derived every day from the maximum of the temperature time series in ICON and in IFS. From this input data, WSD is then computed using the python function `xclim.indices.warm_spell_duration_index` from the python package `xclim.indices`. Figure 3 shows an example python script for the ICON model.

For the planned Hazard Hackathon in WP9.5, we will quantify hazards related to fire (see 4.1.3), heat stress and extreme precipitation. The Hazard Hackathon will take place in October in Wageningen, together with the inclusion of stakeholders, especially from insurance companies. During the Hackathon, maps of the chosen fire, heat stress and extreme precipitation indicators will be produced and delivered as deliverable 9.6. This report is about deliverable 8.4, which is about checking that the IFS and ICON variables required to compute those indicators are part of the output and that python functions/tool boxes exist to compute those indicators.

For heat stress, we will use the heat stress indicator of the wet-bulb temperature T_{wb} . The latter is a heat stress indicator, particularly important to quantify the impact of heat on humans, as it quantifies the capacity of humans to cool through sweating. Required input parameters are pressure p , 2-m temperature, 2-m specific humidity. All those three variables are standard output both from the ICON and IFS model. Using these three variables as input, T_{wb} can then be computed using the python function `wet_bulb_temperature` from the python package `metpy`, see https://unidata.github.io/MetPy/latest/api/generated/metpy.calc.wet_bulb_temperature.html for a description of the function.

For extreme precipitation, we will use extremely wet day precipitation (R99p) and very heavy precipitation days (R20mm), as defined in Standstad et al. (2022). R99p is defined as total annually summed precipitation on days with more daily precipitation than the 99th daily precipitation percentile on wet days in the base period. It thus retains only the wettest days of the simulation period. To compute it, we need daily precipitation output which, as noted earlier, is available both in ICON and IFS. We can then compute R99p by determining first the 99th percentile, using the python function `quantile` and then summing the precipitation over those days. R20mm is a sim-

ilar index, but instead of focusing on the amount, it focuses on the time duration. It is formally defined as the number of days per year with 20 mm or more of precipitation. Using the daily precipitation output, it can easily be computed using the python function `xclim.indices.wetdays` from the python package `xclim.indices`.

4.1.3 Fire weather

Fire weather indicators (FWIs) are computed offline after the Canadian forest fire weather index system (<https://cwfis.cfs.nrcan.gc.ca/background/summary/fwi>), which is the most widely used index system for fire. This system contains six fire indices to account for the effects of fuel moisture and weather on fire behavior: the fine fuel moisture code (FFMC), the Duff moisture code (DMC), the drought code (DC), the initial spread index (ISI), the buildup index (BUI) and the fire weather index (FWI). The first three indices (FFMC, DMC and DC) are fuel moisture codes, characterizing the moisture content of litter (FFMC), of loosely compacted organic layers of moderate depth (DMC) and of deep, compact organic layers (DC). The value of each of these three indices rises as the moisture content decreases. The higher the value, the more easily it will burn. The remaining three fire weather indicators (ISI, BUI and FWI) are fire behavior indices. Their values rise as the fire danger increases. ISI characterizes the fire spread potential by integrating FFMC and surface wind speed. BUI characterizes the fuel available for combustion (equivalent to potential heat release) and is computed by combining DMC and DC into an index. Finally FWI characterizes the frontal fire intensity potential. It is computed based on ISI and BUI and is a general index of fire danger.

The six fire weather indicators are computed on a daily basis and require the following meteorological parameters as input: 2-m temperature, 10-m wind speed and 2-m relative humidity, all at midday (local time), as well as precipitation accumulated over the last 24 h. All these input variables are outputted per default in ICON and IFS. Based on this input, the six fire weather indicators are computed as a postprocessing step. A corresponding Python package has been developed to compute the six fire weather indicators. It is available here: <https://github.com/steidani/FireDanger>. This toolbox will be applied to the NextGEMS output during the Hazard Hackathon, which will take place October 2024 in Wageningen, under participation of stakeholders (insurance companies). During this event, maps of the fire weather indicators will be produced using the developed toolbox and the NextGEMS output. These maps will be delivered under future deliverable 9.6, as planned in WP9.5.

4.2 Required output for the pilot project

For the pilot project on solar power and after discussion with stakeholders, we added the following variables as output (online diagnostics) in the two models: global surface downward radiation and direct surface radiation. From these two outputs, diffuse radiation can be computed using the following formula:

$$S_{\text{dif}} = S_{\text{glob}} - \cos \alpha \cdot S_{\text{dir}}, \quad (1)$$

where S_{dif} is the surface downward diffuse radiation, S_{glob} the surface downward global radiation, S_{dir} the surface downward direct radiation measured in the plane perpendicular to the

Figure 4: Comparison of monthly mean surface downward global radiation S_{glob} in Cabauw, The Netherlands, for ICON (5 km resolution), IFS (9, 4, and 2.8 km resolution) and observations from the Cabauw Baseline Surface Radiation Network site.

zenith, and α is the zenith angle. For solar power production purposes, it is important to be able to separate global radiation into direct and diffuse radiation, because diffuse radiation finds its way to solar panels from the entire hemisphere, and is a source of energy when direct radiation is absent due to the presence of clouds or the orientation of the solar panels. The zenith angle was already an output variable.

For detailed prediction of produced energy by photovoltaics, it can be useful to not only know the broadband global radiation, but also its distribution over its wavelengths, because of the variation of light sensitivity among different materials of which photovoltaic cells are made. To that aim, we added in the ICON model the possibility to select and output radiation in the visible, near-infrared, and photosynthetically active ranges of the frequency bands. All this output is required at high frequency (every 12 min for ICON, hourly for IFS) and is outputted at the 30 stations that were chosen for the high-frequency data logging (see task 8.3 and corresponding deliverable 8.3). These outputs will be heavily used on the final stages of the project, during which the production of a solar power production atlas is foreseen (Deliverable 9.5).

During the cycle 2 hackathon, nextGEMS scientists have worked together with researchers from renewable energy institutes to compare the high-resolution time series of the nextGEMS model runs against observations. Figure 4 (courtesy of Sebastian Zainali) shows the comparison of the storm-resolving models in their ability to reproduce S_{glob} at the Cabauw site in The Netherlands.

The figure shows that the storm-resolving models closely follow the observations, which shows that as a first impression, the models do well in capturing the average state of the cloudiness over Cabauw. Interestingly, there appears to be a small decrease in S_{glob} with increasing resolution in IFS, hinting at an increase in cloud cover with increasing resolution. This finding is under investigation, and will be further explained in work related to deliverable D9.3.

5 References (Bibliography)

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6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The implemented output statistics are necessary for the planned science in WP9 and for the pilot project on solar energy, so they are directly taken up by the targeted audience. The diagnostics are also computed during the Hackathons, thus easily reaching the NextGEMS community.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

No, but this is the resubmission of the deliverable based on the reviewer's comments. The reviewer's comments were that sections 4.1.2 'Extreme' and 4.1.3 'Fire weather' are very generic and that section 4.2 'Required output for the pilot project' can be developed further. We updated sections 4.1.2 and 4.1.3, now focusing on the specific indices that will be computed. Likewise we gave more details on section 4.2. Note that this deliverable is about making sure that the ICON and IFS output as well as the functions needed to compute the chosen indices are present. Computation and detailed report on the indices will be reported in follow-up deliverables. We nonetheless included a couple of examples to illustrate some of the results.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

This task contributes to O1 under A1 and to O3 under A4. It links with the deliverable 8.3 (high-frequency data logging) and especially with deliverables 9.1 (report on the evaluation of atmospheric blocking), 9.2 (report on the evaluation of the characteristics of warm and dry spells), 9.5 (solar energy atlas) and 9.6 (maps of hazardous weather) as the latter four deliverables will apply the developed indices to the NextGEMS output to conduct the foreseen analysis and evaluate the models.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Website <https://nextgems-h2020.eu> online

- Cycle 2 Hackathon, 28.06. - 02.07.2022 in Vienna

11 Full track of publications and IP

No publications so far.